

Beyond One Million Genomes

D2.3 - Core Elements for Data Protection Impact Assessments of providing Cross Border Data Access in the EU to personal genetic Data for research purposes

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1. Executive Summary

1.1 Cross Border Data Access and Data Protection Impact Assessment. The core element of the [Beyond One Million Genomes Project](#) (B1MG) is the provision of access to genomic data of a data subject by a data controller(s) in one Member State(s) to a data user(s) from another Member State(s) ("Cross Border Data Access"). As the provision of Cross Border Data Access is likely to involve the processing of (directly or indirectly) identifying data (personal data), it is likely to be subject to the EU General Data Protection Regulation ("GDPR"). As the processing concerns the processing, on a large-scale, of special categories of data (i.e. genetic data and data concerning health), the processing is deemed by GDPR to be likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects concerned. Specifically, the provision of Cross Border Access will exacerbate these risks, as (i) it could be subject to diverging, if not conflicting, sector-specific national Member State laws, regulations and codes, (ii) the GDPR allows Member States a 'margin to manoeuvre' with respect to processing of personal data for research purposes, which inter alia allows a Member State to derogate from various GDPR data subject rights, and (iii) under the GDPR, Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health consensus on the envisaged data flows, risk types and levels, and standard-setting related to privacy and security safeguards. Consequently, a controller providing Cross Border Data Access must, ex ante, carry out an assessment of the impact of the provision of Cross Border Data Access on the protection of personal data (Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)).

1.2 Common Elements for a DPIA of Cross Border Data Access. The 1+MG projects builds in part on existing (national or local) data collections. We assume that the controllers of these collections and cohorts already conduct their own DPIAs with respect to the data these collections contain and may therefore be hesitant to perform a separate DPIA for the processing under 1+MG projects. Therefore the following sets forth a number of Common Elements for a DPIA which specifically address the cross border aspects, as an "add on" to existing DPIAs, with the aim to coordinate the identification, assessment, and mitigation of the data protection issues triggered by Cross Border Data Access. Establishing Common Elements should also help achieve shared standards or approaches for the safeguards for the rights and freedoms of data subjects required under GPDR, for example the use of remote access, pseudonimisation and governance of access. The Common Elements are expressly limited to Cross Border Data Access for purposes of scientific research processing operations by healthcare providers for clinical purposes, but are amenable to "upgraded" for healthcare purposes.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'.]

Objective/Key Result No & Description	Contributed
Objective 1: Engage local, regional, national and European stakeholders to define the requirements for cross-border access to genomics and personalised medicine data	
1: B1MG assembles key local, national, European and global actors in the field of Personalised Medicine within a B1MG Stakeholder Coordination Group (WP1) by M6.	No
2: B1MG drives broad engagement around European access to personalised medicine data via the B1MG Stakeholder Coordination Portal (WP1) following the B1MG Communication Strategy (WP6) by M12.	No
3: B1MG establishes awareness and dialogue with a broad set of societal actors via a continuously monitored and refined communications strategy (WP1, WP6) by M12, M18, M24 & M30.	Yes
4: The open B1MG Summit (M18) engages and ensures that the views of all relevant stakeholders are captured in B1MG requirements and guidelines (WP1, WP6).	Yes
Objective 2: Translate requirements for data quality, standards, technical infrastructure, and ELSI into technical specifications and implementation guidelines that captures European best practice	
Legal & Ethical Key Results	
1: Establish relevant best practice in ethics of cross-border access to genome and phenotypic data (WP2) by M36	Yes
2: Analysis of legal framework and development of common minimum standard (WP2) by M36.	Yes
3: Cross-border Data Access and Use Governance Toolkit Framework (WP2) by M36.	Yes
Technical Key Results	
4: Quality metrics for sequencing (WP3) by M12.	No
5: Best practices for Next Generation Sequencing (WP3) by M24.	No
6: Phenotypic and clinical metadata framework (WP3) by M12, M24 & M36.	No
7: Best practices in sharing and linking phenotypic and genetic data (WP3) by M12 & M24.	Yes
8: Data analysis challenge (WP3) by M36.	No

Infrastructure Key Results	
9: Secure cross-border data access roadmap (WP4) by M12 & M36.	Yes
10: Secure cross-border data access demonstrator (WP4) by M24.	Yes
Objective 3: Drive adoption and support long-term operation by organisations at local, regional, national and European level by providing guidance on phased development (via the B1MG maturity level model), and a methodology for economic evaluation	
1: The B1MG maturity level model (WP5) by M24.	Yes
2: Roadmap and guidance tools for countries for effective implementation of Personalised Medicine (WP5) by M36.	No
3: Economic evaluation models for Personalised Medicine and case studies (WP5) by M30.	No
4: Guidance principles for national mirror groups and cross-border Personalised Medicine governance (WP6) by M30.	Yes
5: Long-term sustainability design and funding routes for cross-border Personalised Medicine delivery (WP6) by M34.	No

3. Methods

The following Common Elements have been set up following the guidance issued by the Article 29 Working Party Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679.¹

4. Description of work accomplished

The work has resulted in a draft set of Common Elements and considerations for DPIAs of providing Cross Border Access in the EU to personal data for scientific research. Specifically, the Core elements discuss the Need for a DPIA, the Context of the DPIA, Consultation with data subjects, the necessity and proportionality of the provision of Cross Border Access, Identification and Assessment of Risks and proposed, sample, measures and safeguards to mitigate those risks.

4. Results

See set of Common Elements set forth below.

5. Discussion

To be provided after finalising current draft

6. Conclusions

¹ Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, adopted on 4 April 2017, as last Revised and Adopted on 4 October 2017, endorsed by European Data Protection Board during its first plenary meeting on May 25, 2018.

To be provided after finalising current draft.

8. Next steps

To turn the Draft Common Elements in a definitive version, the following next steps are envisaged:

1. Input will be sought from the pertinent WPs and WGs. Ideally this input will foster alignment and consensus on the proposed standards and safeguards
2. Final version will be produced.

[Half to one page]

9. Impact

The Common Elements for a DPIA which specifically address the cross border aspects, as an "add on" to existing DPIAs, aim to coordinate the identification, assessment, and mitigation of the data protection issues triggered by Cross Border Data Access. Establishing Common Elements should also help achieve shared standards or approaches for the safeguards for the rights and freedoms of data subjects required under GDPR, for example the use of remote access, pseudonimisation and governance of access. The Common Elements are expressly limited to Cross Border Data Access for purposes of scientific research processing operations by healthcare providers for clinical purposes, but are amenable to "upgraded" for the provision of Cross Border Access for healthcare purposes.

Core Elements and Considerations for Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) of providing Cross Border Access in the EU to personal genetic Data for scientific research purposes

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BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Core Element # 1: Controller details

Name of controller(s)	(Name of entity providing Cross Border Access for scientific research purposes).
Subject/title of DPIA	Providing Cross Border Access to personal genetic data.

Name of controller contact/DPO and contact details.	
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BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Core Element # 2: Summary

Introduction

1.1 The provision of Cross Border Access to Genomic Data for scientific research. Genomics research stands to benefit from providing researchers across the EU with access to genomic information stored across the EU. The provision of such access to genomic data of a data subject by a data controller in one Member State to a data user(s) from another Member State(s) ("Cross Border Access") is likely to involve the processing of (directly or indirectly) identifying data (personal data) and hence subject to the EU General Data Protection Regulation ("GDPR").

1.2 Scope of DPIA of Cross Border Access. As the provision of Cross Border Access involves the processing, on a large-scale, of special categories of data (i.e. genetic data and data concerning health), it is deemed by GDPR to be likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects concerned. Consequently, we, as controller providing Cross Border Access shall, prior to our provision, carry out an assessment of the impact of these processing operations on the protection of personal data (Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)). The scope of this DPIA is our provision of Cross Border Access, as detailed below.

1.3 Impact on Rights and Freedoms of data subjects. For this DPIA, we have identified the risks and assessed the impact of our provision of providing Cross Border Access on the rights and freedoms of the data subjects concerned, as required under GDPR. We considered that the leakage of identifying information i genetic and omics data has been established in many studies, with single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) shown to carry a strong risk of reidentification for individuals and their genetic relatives. We then considered the sensitive nature of genetic data, the repeated use thereof through Cross Border Access by multiple data users, from a variety of jurisdictions, each with their own rules and regulations, the resultant accumulation of meaning to be ascribed to the data, the possible requirement of feedback of results to the data subject and her family and the potential of this type of data and associated information being abused, whether or not by linking with other personal data, resulting in economic or social disadvantage, including discrimination and limitation or denial of access to private and public services, loss of autonomy, automated decision-making and coercive or mandatory medicines, for the data subject or her family.

In addition, we considered that Cross Border Access will exacerbate these risks, as (i) the processing of the data could be subject to diverging, if not conflicting, sector-specific national Member State laws, regulations and codes, (ii) the GDPR allows Member States a 'margin to manoeuvre' with respect to processing of personal data for research purposes, which inter alia allows a Member State to derogate from various GDPR data subject rights, and (iii) under the GDPR, Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health. Our assessment concludes that the impact provision of Cross Border Access constitutes high risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects concerned and their family members.

1.4 Measures to mitigate impact. To mitigate the above risks, we have taken technical and organizational measures, which offer, in view of the high risks involved, the commitments made to the data subjects and the necessity maintain trust among data subjects, their family members and the public, protection at source and meet the highest possible standards.

1.5 Endpoint: prior consultation. In view of the risks identified and assessed, both in terms of likelihood and severity, and the measures taken by us to reduce these risks, we have submitted this DPIA to the competent Supervisory Authority for prior consultation.

BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Core Element # 3: The need for a DPIA

1.1 Cross Border Access to personal genetic data. This Cross Border Access project involves the provision of access to certain genomic data of certain data subjects by Us as Data Access Provider to one or more Data User(s) established in another Member State(s), for purposes of scientific research. The data to be processed under the Cross Border Access Project include but are not limited to, genomes (Whole Genome Sequences (WGS), exomes (Whole Exome Sequences (WES), phenotypes and clinical data. WGS (and WES?) data are being processed in the following formats: FASTQ, BAM, CRAM, gVCF.²

1.2 Processing special categories of personal data. The data to be processed as part of the Cross Border Access project are personal data as defined in the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), meaning that (i) there exist technical means which (ii) make it reasonably likely that such data could be used to identify a living person. Even if a reasonable case could be made for why some of the data would not qualify as personal data, our risk approach is to treat these as personal data anyway. By definition these data qualify as special category data under GDPR: genetic data, data concerning health.

1.3 Need for DPIA. As controller(s) providing Cross Border Access to the genomic data concerned, we are subject to the obligation under GDPR to conduct a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), as this processing is deemed under GDPR likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. This is, inter alia, because our provision of Cross Border Access involves special categories of personal data as defined in Article 9 GDPR (genetic and health data), the processing thereof on a large scale, the potential of the matching of combining of datasets,³ the sensitive nature of the data concerned, the potential repeated use thereof through Cross Border Access by multiple data users, from a variety of jurisdictions, each with their own rules and regulations, the resultant accumulation of meaning to be ascribed to the data, the possible requirement of feedback of results to the data subject and her family and the potential of this type of data and associated information being abused, whether or not by linking with other personal data, resulting in economic or social disadvantage, including discrimination and limitation or denial of access to private and public services, loss of autonomy, automated decision-making and coercive or mandatory medicines, for the data subject or her family. In addition, we considered that our provision of Cross Border Access will exacerbate these risks, as (i) the processing of the data could be subject to diverging, if not conflicting, sector-specific national Member State laws, regulations and codes, (ii) the GDPR allows Member States a 'margin to manoeuvre' with respect to processing of personal data for research purposes, which inter alia allows a Member State to derogate from various GDPR data subject rights, and (iii) under the GDPR, Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health.

1.4 Stage of project at which DPIA was carried out. This DPIA has been carried out prior to our provision of Cross Border Access.

² <https://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/>

³ Article 35 GDPR.

1.5 Methodology. We have conducted this DPIA following the guidance issued by the Article 29 Working Party "Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679".⁴ As a DPIA must be based on the specific facts of the processing activities concerned, it is preceded by a description of the context of the Cross Border Access project.

1.6 Involvement of Data Protection Officer. As per GDPR requirement, we sought the advice of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) on our conduct of this DPIA. The DPO has provided advice as regards the DPIA and monitored its performance. The involvement of the DPO as well as his/her final advice has been documented and attached hereto as Annex 1 hereto. The DPO has submitted his/her advice directly to the highest management level of our organisation.

BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Core Element # 4: Context

1.1 Context. The Cross Border Data Access project is described in detail in the Data User's Cross Border Access project proposal/request, the accompanying research protocol and the accompanying data management plan, all linked/attached hereto [insert link or attachment]. The data life Cycle Cross Border Access project can be summarized as follows [Insert summary].

1.2. Data Provenance and Data donors. The provision of Cross Border Access involves personal genetic data derived from samples from [patients diagnosed with ; family of patients; healthy volunteers]. Said samples have been collected from living or post-mortem donors or both.

1.3 Purpose of the provision of Cross Border Access. The provision of Cross Border Access is for the purpose of scientific research into .

1.4 Cross Border Access Provider. In the process of providing Cross Border Access, We, as the Cross Border Data Access Provider, may be processing personal data regarding Cross Border Data Access Users, for example information necessary to create or access a Cross Border Data Access User account, such as a Cross Border Data Access User's name, username, email address, and login credentials. Cross Border Data Access User Data is any information We will process from a third party researcher seeking or having been granted Cross Border Data Access (User Data). This DPIA does not cover our processing of User Data.

BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Core Element # 5: Consultation with data subjects

1.1 Consultation with data subjects or their representatives. When performing a DPIA, controllers are required, under GDPR, to seek the views of data subjects or their representatives on the intended processing, without prejudice to the protection of commercial or public interests or the security of processing operations, where appropriate. We have set up a mechanism enabling this consultation, reaching out to individual patients, where appropriate, or their representative organisations. The outcome of this consultation is attached hereto as Annex 2. The recommendations of the consultation have been incorporated in the mitigation measures set forth below.

⁴ Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, adopted on 4 April 2017, as last Revised and Adopted on 4 October 2017, endorsed by European Data Protection Board during its first plenary meeting on May 25, 2018.

BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Core Element # 6: Necessity and proportionality

1.1 Necessity. Under GDPR, processing of personal data must be limited to what is necessary in relation to the purpose for which they are processed. Specifically, personal data may be processed for scientific research purposes on the conditions that (i) such processing is subject to appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subject and (ii) where the scientific purpose can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of the data subjects, this research purpose should be fulfilled in that manner. Having assessed the request for the Cross Border Data Access, we have concluded that it []is/[]is not] necessary to process *personal* data to achieve the purposes of the scientific research described therein and that the purposes of said research []can/[]cannot] be achieved without the use of (indirectly) identifying data and have concluded that [..]. NB: claim that use of personal data is necessary must be substantiated, e.g. why not possible to work with synthetic data?

1.2 Proportionality; data minimization. To meet this requirement, i.e. that the processing of personal data is proportionate to the purposes of the processing thereof, we have mechanisms in place to ensure (i) not more data is being provided than necessary for the purposes of an approved research project, and (ii) that, where the research purpose can be fulfilled by processing which no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner. These measures include, but are not limited to, the measures set forth below.

BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Core Element # 7: Identification and assessment of risks

1.1 Identification of risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects. A DPIA is to assess the risks of a type of processing to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. Recital 75 of the GDPR sums up these risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, of varying likelihood and severity, which may result from personal data processing which could lead to physical, material or non-material damage, in particular:

- o *where the processing may give rise to discrimination, identity theft or fraud, financial loss, damage to the reputation, loss of confidentiality of personal data protected by professional secrecy, unauthorised reversal of pseudonymisation, or any other significant economic or social disadvantage;*
- o *where data subjects might be deprived of their rights and freedoms or prevented from exercising control over their personal data;*
- o *where personal data are processed which reveal racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religion or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, and*
- o *the processing of genetic data, data concerning health or data concerning sex life or criminal convictions and offences or related security measures;*
- o *where personal aspects are evaluated, in particular analysing or predicting aspects concerning performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, location or movements, in order to create or use personal profiles;*
- o *where personal data of vulnerable natural persons, in particular of children, are processed; or where processing involves a large amount of personal data and affects a large number of data subjects.*

1.2 Assessment of risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects and their family. For this DPIA, we have identified the risks and assessed the impact of our provision of providing Cross Border Access

on the rights and freedoms of the data subjects concerned, as required under GDPR. We considered that the leakage of identifying information i genetic and omics data has been established in many studies, with single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) shown to carry a strong risk of reidentification for individuals and their genetic relatives. We then considered the sensitive nature of the data concerned, the repeated use thereof through Cross Border Access by multiple data users, from a variety of jurisdictions, each with their own rules and regulations, the resultant accumulation of meaning to be ascribed to the data, the possible requirement of feedback of results to the data subject and her family and the potential of this type of data and associated information being abused, whether or not by linking with other personal data, resulting in economic or social disadvantage, including discrimination and limitation or denial of access to private and public services, loss of autonomy, automated decision-making and coercive or mandatory medicines, for the data subject or her family. In addition, we considered that Cross Border Access will exacerbate these risks, as (i) the processing of the data could be subject to diverging, if not conflicting, sector-specific national Member State laws, regulations and codes, (ii) the GDPR allows Member States a 'margin to manoeuvre' with respect to processing of personal data for research purposes, which inter alia allows a Member State to derogate from various GDPR data subject rights, and (iii) under the GDPR, Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health. Our assessment concludes that the impact provision of Cross Border Access constitutes high risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects concerned and their family members.

BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Core Element #8: Measures & (Sample) Safeguards

1.1. Overview of mitigating measures and safeguards. To mitigate these risks, we have taken a series of strategic, technical and organizational measures, which in our view provide appropriate safeguards as required under Article 89 GDPR, which are set forth below.

Safeguards: General

- Sample Safeguard: Personal Genome Locker

For provision of Cross Border Data Access, use is made of the pertinent data subject's Personal Genetic Locker (PGL). This PGL⁵ is a proposed Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructure which allows the data subject to store and access their own genetic (and health) data, understand the health implications, add their own health-related information and consent to or refuse sharing with treating physicians, and/or use for research projects, including the provision of Cross Border Data Access. Offering a decentralised approach, the PGL enables the data subject (patient/individual) to exercise full control about the use of his or her genetic data, including the option of dynamic consent, and provides a tool to handle the feedback of any (incidental) research findings resulting from the provision of Cross Border Access.

- Sample Safeguard: Remote/Federated Analysis

⁵ Using Personal Genomic Data within Primary Care: A Bioinformatics Approach to Pharmacogenomics, Overkleeft et al., *Genes* **2020**, *11*, 1443; doi:10.3390/genes11121443.

We will provide Cross Border Data Access by way of remote/federated non-disclosive analysis (aka distributed or decentralised analysis). Cross Border Data Access Users will be provided the ability to perform complex analysis tasks on decentralised data by "bringing their analysis to the data" rather than by "bringing the data subject's data to their analysis". Preventing the data from leaving their location and from being centralised, will ensure we meet our requirement of data minimization and offers optimal protection of the rights and freedoms of data subjects. Several Remote Analysis tools have been developed, including without limitation:

- Sample safeguard: [DATA SHIELD](#). *"DATA SHIELD is open-source software for the remote/federated non-disclosive analysis of biomedical, healthcare and social-science data. Crucially, the data remain secure behind the firewalls of the system where they usually reside and under the complete control of their primary custodian. Analytical commands are then sent to the data. Analysts are prevented from seeing or copying the individual-level data (microdata) that underpin the analyses required and yet those same analyses are typically fully efficient from a statistical perspective. Embedded privacy-protection traps guard actively against - and facilitate detection of attempts based on analytical results to identify individual data subjects or to infer the value of particular variables in subjects. DATA SHIELD can also be useful when the underlying data objects are too large to physically share. DATASHIELD is used in both research and healthcare settings can be applied to a wide range of data types. Its analytical capability has recently been extended to encompass high-volume 'omics data and other large datasets. Most extant use-cases involve federated multi-study co-analysis across international boundaries, but DATASHIELD also supports the privacy-protected analysis of data from a single source."*

- Sample Safeguard: [Personal Health Train](#). *"The essence of the Personal Health Train (PHT) approach is that the research question travels to the datasource 'stations' rather than data from various sources having to be transported to the research question. So, sensitive data remains where it is. The PHT can transport 'workflows' for complex research questions; 'Which data elements are most predictive of survival after lung cancer given all data in the Netherlands?'; or more specific: 'Which data stations contain data about me?' The PHT connects different data 'stations'. Stations can range from very large databases to small personal lockers containing the data of one person. Each station has its own set of house rules describing what a visiting 'train' is allowed to do with their data. Ranging from 'nobody can do anything' to 'anyone can use this element as they wish'. Large scale application of the PHT requires that health data is [FAIR](#) (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)."*

Safeguard: Pseudonimisation

The appropriate safeguards required under GDPR for processing personal data for scientific research purposes may include pseudonimisation. When providing Cross Border Data Access we use the following pseudonimisation techniques:

- Sample Pseudonimisation Safeguard: [privacy-preserving-BAM files \("pBAM"\)](#). *"pBAM is to allow the sharing of raw human genome aligned sequences to the community without restriction, while at the same time protecting the privacy of the individuals. The underlying assumption is the identifying information in the sequences such as SNPs, indels or large structural variants are not necessary to quantify the expression of the genes or functional annotation of important genomic regions that can be captured by assays such as ATAC-Seq and ChIP-Seq. To this end, we manipulate the BAM files such that any feature of the BAM*

that has any indication of a variant is generalized to a value that does not leak any information about the presence of a variant."

- Other, notably [..].

Safeguards: Data Security, Confidentiality, Integrity

- Sample Security Safeguard: [Storing and analyzing a Genome on a Blockchain](#). A critical barrier to expanding personal genome sequencing is achieving secure, high-integrity storage of raw data. While cloud storage offers solutions to access such data from any place and device, the vulnerabilities of centralized storage in relation to security, data integrity, and robustness, such as single points of failure, have not yet been addressed. Blockchain is a potential alternative to these storage modes. However, storing large-scale data on blockchain can be challenging due to slow transaction speeds, the potential for chains to reach large sizes, and limitations on querying data stored on-chain. Currently, several genomic storage applications incorporate blockchain, but likely because of these challenges, many use blockchain only to facilitate and log data-access transactions, rather than to store raw genomic data on-chain. While this secures the process of data access, it does not secure the data itself, which is often stored off-chain (i.e. in a cloud or file-hosting services). Here, we developed a novel method of storing reference-aligned reads on-chain in a private blockchain network. We also developed tools for accessing and analyzing the on-chain data. We addressed the challenges of on-chain data storage by minimizing the data inserted to the chain using reference-based data compression techniques and by binning the on-chain data by genomic location to reduce retrieval times. Our tools provide open-source blockchain-based storage and access for advanced genomic analyses such as variant calling.

- Sample safeguard: Information Security Program: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/>. Our Information Security program implements and maintains controls that align with the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) cybersecurity certification schemes;

- Safeguard: Incident Response. We have an established process that is followed whenever it detects suspicious or abnormal activity with respect to Cross Border Data Access that might have a security implication. In order to support this process and its efforts to ensure that the Cross Border Data Access is available, our engineering and security teams have on call rotations to provide a designated point person available to respond to any suspicious or abnormal activity. As part of Our incident response process, We perform postmortem reviews of major incidents including both security and nonsecurity related (such as site outages). These postmortem reviews are designed to ensure that it learns from past incidents and if needed, improve the Cross Border Data Access to prevent them from occurring again in the future.

- Sample Safeguard: Virtual Private Cloud. Our Cross Border Data Access hosted infrastructure resides in a dedicated Virtual Private Cloud (VPC) which is designed to ensure that only authorized traffic over approved ports is allowed. Development infrastructure resides in a separate VPC. We have services built in to monitor for suspicious activity.

Safeguard: Authentication and Authorisation.

- Safeguard Authentication and Authorisation. We will only provide Cross Border Data Access to authenticated and authorised researchers. To check authentication and authorisation, we will of an the Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI).

Safeguard: Controlled Access

- We will provide Cross Border Data Access to qualified researchers for approved use only. Cross Border Access will be governed by the provisions laid out in the associated informed consent of the pertinent individual data subjects and any additional conditions imposed by the pertinent ethics committee which approved of the primary collection of the data. the Data Access Procedure set forth below and the terms of the Data Access Agreement attached hereto. A qualified researcher refers to a senior investigator who is employed or legitimately affiliated with an academic, non-profit or government institution and who has a track record in the field.

- Cross Border Data Access is available by application to the Cross Border Data Access Committee. Cross Border Data Access is conditional upon availability of data and on signed agreement by the researcher(s) and the responsible employing institution to abide by the policies and conditions related to publication, data ownership, data return, intellectual property rights, data disposal, ethical approval, confidentiality and commercialization referred in the Cross Border Data Access Agreement.

- Data Access Procedure. A data user may request Cross Border Data Access to Our Cross Border Data Access Committee which is established in the home state of the data subject, as follows:

Access request. The handling of applications, the provision of Cross Border Data Access and any associated operations, administration and audits will be performed by us as the Cross Border Data Access provider. Applications for Cross Border Data Access must be submitted using an Application Form for Cross Border Data Access Data issued by Us. The information disclosed in the application will be treated as confidential and will only be disclosed to the persons evaluating the application. All incoming applications will be documented, including any conjunct agreements with the applicants. Unless explicitly consented for by the applicant, this information will not be used for purposes other than evaluation of the application. The research topic of the applications which have been granted will be published on the website of the data provider. Applications which have not been granted will not be published. In cases where an application contains classified plans, know-how or trade secrets, the applicant may request the conclusion of a separate confidentiality agreement.

Multiple applications. Applicants agree to Cross Border Data Access for the approved purpose and project described in their application as granted; use of the data Cross Border Data Access for a new purpose or project will require a new application and approval. Our Cross Border Data Access Committee will consider applications that include named collaborators, but each Cross Border Data Access User must co-sign the application. In the event two or more applications overlap, the Cross Border Data Access Committee may propose the respective applicants to align their applications.

Assessment criteria. Applications which seek to Cross Border Data Access for unspecified research goals will not be taken into consideration. Specifically, the BMGENOMES DAC will assess each application for access to determine whether:

- (i) it has been submitted by a qualified researcher or researchers, who is employed by or legitimately affiliated with a recognised research institution that can provide institutional responsibility for appropriate research governance;

- (ii) its proposed Cross Border Data Access is in accordance with and meets the objectives of our data collection;
- (iii) its proposed Cross Border Data Access conforms to the individual data subject 's informed consent;
- (iv) it does not breach any of the ethical permissions or restrictions in the consent form for the data subject concerned;
- (v) all required ethico-legal approvals, restrictions and commitments for the proposed Cross Border Data Access have been obtained and adhered to;
- (vi) the proposed Cross Border Data Access has no adverse potential impact, and specifically does not adversely affect minorities;
- (vii) the nature of the funding of the application and the applicant;
- (viii) the research proposal has been peer-reviewed, and, if not, whether the proposal satisfies applicable scientific standards;
- (ix) the requested data are, quantitatively and qualitatively, suitable and not excessive for the applicant's proposed research;
- (x) there are any similar applications pending or granted;
- (xi) the proposed Cross Border Data Access has the potential to produce information that will enable identification of the individual data subjects.
- (xii) the applicant has warranted that he has obtained all ethico-legal approvals, restrictions and commitments, required under the laws of his country of establishment jurisdiction, including, without limitation, the informed consent of her own data subjects consent and approval of her pertinent medical ethical review board, for his proposed use of his data in combination with Cross border Data Access.

Access decision. The Cross border Data Access Committee will decide on an application within a reasonable period of time after it has received all pertinent information. Approvals and rejections of applications will be motivated by the DAC. Applications which have been approved will be published on the website of the data provider.

1.2 Endpoint: residual risk. One of the endpoints of a DPIA is to assess whether a controller is obliged to consult the supervisory authority prior to its processing of the data. This will be the case where the DPIA indicates that the processing would result in a high risk in the absence of measures taken to mitigate the risk. In view of the risks identified and assessed, both in terms of likelihood and severity, and the measures we take and safeguards we have in place, and in view of the consultation with data subjects and/or data subjects' representatives, we consider that our provision of Cross Border Data Access will result in a high risk that requires a prior consultation with the competent supervisory authority.

BMG Cross Border Access DPIA - Sign off and record outcomes

Item	Name/position/date	Notes

Measures approved by:		Integrate actions back into project plan, with date and responsibility for completion
Residual risks approved by:		If accepting any residual high risk, consult the competent supervisory authority before going ahead
DPO advice provided:		DPO should advise on compliance, measures and safeguards and whether processing can proceed
Summary of DPO advice:		
DPO advice accepted or overruled by:		If overruled, you must explain your reasons
Comments:		
Consultation responses reviewed by:		If your decision departs from individuals' views, you must explain your reasons

Comments:		
This DPIA will kept under review by:		The DPO should also review ongoing compliance with DPIA

Annex 1 - Involvement of DPO

Annex 2 - Outcome of consultation with data subjects/data subjects' representatives

